

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

FORMULATION AND EVALUTION OF GASTRORETENTIVE MUCOADHESIVE TABLETS OF ANTIRETROVIRAL DRUG

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 11/05/2018

Available online

15/06/2018

Keywords

Zidovudine,
GRDDS,
Mucoadhesive,
Bioavailability.

ABSTRACT

Objective: The aim in the present investigation was to design and evaluate the gastro retentive mucoadhesive delivery system of Zidovudine with a view to enhance the gastric residence time and its oral bioavailability. In the current work, direct compression method has been employed to prepare GRDDS of Zidovudine with HPMC K100M, NaCMC, Carbopol934P and PVP K30 with different drug to polymer ratios. Various evaluation tests and stability tests were conducted. Pre formulation studies for all formulations showed satisfactory results. FTIR studies evidenced that drugs and polymers were compatible. Followed by The formulated tablets were subjected for various evaluation parameters like hardness (3.98 ± 0.654 to 3.09 ± 0.455 kg/cm²), thickness (2.98 ± 0.13 - 2.29 ± 0.09 mm), weight variation (303.69 ± 1.428 - 298.35 ± 1.006 mg), drug content (100.65 ± 0.45 - 97.81 ± 0.590 mg), friability (0.75 ± 0.04 - 0.45 ± 0.07), results showed all extensively passed, all the evaluation tests as per USP standards. Swelling index, mucoadhesive strength, Ex-Vivo Residence Time results were propositional to concentration polymers. In dissolution study it was observed that release of Zidovudine from different formulations was spread over a period of 8-12hrs depending on the polymer's concentration and viscosity. Among various formulations studied, F13 containing HPMC K100M and NaCMC showed 99.98% drug release at the end of 12hrs and found to be stable at 40 °C and 75% RH following a three month stability study.

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Please cite this article in press as **Mohammad Bakhatwar et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Gastroretentive Mucoadhesive Tablets of Antiretroviral Drug. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. 2018;8(05).**

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INTRODUCTION

The oral route is most widely preferable and acceptable route for the delivery of drugs to the systemic circulation because of their easy administration, convenience of patient and very flexible etc. After administration of the drug orally, the drug absorbed from the sustained release preparations depends on the transit time to get absorbed into GIT [1]. An important adverse effect regarding the controlled release oral systems is the dosage form which rapidly transports the drug from the region of maximum absorption to the region where the drugs not absorbed well. Drugs that absorb into the gastrointestinal system, slow release preparations of such drugs reach lower regions of the GIT; its absorption is reduced before the medicament is completely released [2].

There are some drugs which have categorized as 'Once a day' to demonstrate the suboptimal absorption which is due to dependence of dosage form on the transit time, making traditional extended release development challenging. There is a system which is designed for the absorption of the drug into the small intestine to extend the gastric holding time of the drug in the GIT. The bioavailability of the drugs and retention time of the drug in GIT can be increased by formulating the drug into controlled release systems [3]. Recent approach to enhance the gastric retentive time of delivery system of the drug include (1) bio adhesive device, (2) system that are smaller and rapidly increase in size, (3) gastro-retentive floating systems which have low density. The drug get released in the stomach and the upper parts of small intestine [4].

Zidovudine is a prodrug and analog of thymidine derivative which selectively inhibits the HIV's reverse transcriptase, enzyme which makes to use a DNA copy of its RNA which is responsible to produce HIV double stranded DNA, which integrates into the genetic material of infected cell. It weakly inhibits the cellular DNA polymerase α and γ . Zidovudine convert into effective 5'-triphosphate form by cellular enzymes. As the zidovudine possess the first pass metabolism, the zidovudine capsule's and its solution's bioavailability is nearly about 65% (i.e. ranges from 52 to 75%) [5].

The biological half life of the zidovudine is 3-5 hrs. The binding property of the zidovudine to the plasma proteins is about 30-38% which is said to be very low. It absorbs completely and rapidly into GIT expected that "mucoadhesive delivery system" brings a great proximity to the drug by expecting more absorption phenomena and said to be therapeutically optimum that reduce drug dose and shows effective treatment. In the current investigation, the work has made on the zidovudine, to increase the extent of rate of absorption by formulating the drug as a mucoadhesive drug delivery system. Reduction of drug dose will decrease the development of the resistance and toxicity to Zidovudine.

In the current work, an effort has been made to formulate GRDDS of Zidovudine using various mucoadhesive polymers like HPMC K100M, NaCMC, Carbopol 934P and PVP K30 to extend the drug release, and to impart mucoadhesive properties to the controlled release tablet formulations.

The main objective was to design and evaluate the gastro retentive mucoadhesive delivery system of Zidovudine with a view to enhance its oral bioavailability.

MATERIAL

Zidovudine was obtained as gift sample from kp labs Ltd. (Hyderabad, India) Sodium CMC(S.d. Fine chemicals limited Mumbai), HPMC K100M(S.d. Fine chemicals limited Mumbai), PVP K30(S.d. Fine chemicals limited Mumbai), Carbopol(S.d. Fine chemicals limited Mumbai), Lactose(S.d. Fine chemicals limited Mumbai) Magnesium stearate(S.d. Fine chemicals limited Mumbai), Talc(S.d. Fine chemicals limited Mumbai), All reagents were of pharmaceutical grade and were used as received.

METHODOLOGY

FT- IR:

Compatibility between the drugs and excipients was known by subjecting the physical mixture of the sample and the polymers of the formulation to infrared absorption spectral analysis (FTIR). After combining the polymers with the drug the changes in the drug's chemical proportions were examined with IR spectral analysis.

Preparation of gastro retentive mucoadhesive tablets of Zidovudine

In the current work, direct compression method has been employed to prepare GRDDS of Zidovudine with HPMC K100M, NaCMC, Carbopol934P and PVP K30, with different drug to polymer ratios as per the composition given in following table. Lactose has been used as diluents. Magnesium stearate was used as lubricant and talc as glidant [6].

Table-1: Formula for the preparation of gastro retentive mucoadhesive tablets of Zidovudine.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13
Zidovudine	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
HPMC K100M	50	75	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	37.5	50	37.5	50
Sodium CMC	-	-	-	50	75	100	-	-	-	-	-	37.5	50
Carbopol	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	75	100	37.5	50	-	-
PVP K-30	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Lactose	120	95	70	120	95	70	120	95	70	95	70	95	70
Mg.Stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Evaluation parameter:**Determination of precompression parameters****Bulk density**

Bulk density is the ratio of mass of the loose powder and its known volume. It was determined by accurately weighing the test sample of mass M and placing it into 25 mL dry measuring cylinder without compacting. The sample was levelled carefully without compacting and the apparent volume V_o and the value which was nearer to graduated unit was noted. Bulk density was calculated, in g/mL, by the formula [7].

$$\rho_o = M/V_o$$

Tapped density

The known weight of sample powder was taken in a measuring cylinder and tapped for a standard time and the volume (V_t) was noted. The tapped density can be measured by using the formula [7],

$$\rho_t = M/V_t$$

Carr's index

The flow of powders can be measured easily and simply by using this flow property, it was calculated as follows [7]

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100$$

Hausner's ratio

Hausner's ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow. It is calculated by [7],

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

Angle of repose (θ):

Angle of repose determines the frictional forces of the particles. This is the maximum possible angle between the horizontal plane and the surface of a pile of powder. The powder was passed to flow through the funnel which is fixed to a stand at definite height. It was then calculated by measuring the height and radius of the heap of powder formed using the formula [7],

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$$

Where, h = Height of the pile, r = Radius of the pile and θ is the angle of repose.

Post compression parameters**Hardness Test:**

Hardness is the "force applied to break a tablet in diametric compression test." Hardness is, also said to be tablet crushing strength. The crushing strength (Kg/cm²) of tablets was evaluated by using Monsanto hardness tester. In most of the cases, mean of three replicate determinations were taken [8].

Thickness:

Thickness of tablet is important for uniformity of tablet size. Thickness was determined using Vernier callipers. It was evaluated by checking ten tablets from each formulation [8].

Friability Test:

This was evaluated by placing about 10 tablets which were weighed initially and tumbled in rotating drums with baffles at about 25rpm for 4min, when the process was stopped then the tablets were removed from the apparatus and the samples were finally weighed, then the difference between the initial and final weights should be calculated and finally the percent friability was calculated according to, [8]

$$\% \text{Friability} = [(W_1 - W_2)/W_1] \times 100$$

Where, W_1 = weight of tablets before test, W_2 = weight of tablets after test

Weight variation:

20 tablets were taken and weighed individually on a digital weighing balance. Average weight was calculated and each tablet weight was compared to the average. The tablet pass the U.S.P. test if more than 2 tablets are not outside the percentage limit and if tablet not differs by more than 2 times the percentage limit [8].

Estimation of drug content:

From each formulation about five tablets were powdered. The powdered sample equivalent to 100mg of drug was transferred to a 100ml volumetric flask. 10ml of HCl was added and shaken. The filtrate was diluted with media and analyzed using UV spectrophotometer against blank [8].

Water uptake studies or determination of swelling index:

Initial weight (W_1) of tablet was taken and is placed in 200ml of 0.1N HCl (pH1.2) in a beaker. The tablet was taken out from beaker at each regular interval of time and blotted with filter paper to remove excess of water. Then the tablet was immediately weighed, placed into the same beaker and the final weight (W_2) of the tablet was noted and the test was performed upto 6hr. The swelling index was determined using the following formula [9].

$$\text{Swelling index} = [(W_2 - W_1) / W_1] * 100$$

In vitro mucoadhesive strength:

The tablet's Mucoadhesive strength was measured on a modified physical balance employing the method using goat gastric mucosa as model mucosal membrane. The mucosa was collected from the local slaughter house and placed in Tyrode solution until use. A double beam physical balance was taken, the left pan was removed. A thick thread was hanged to the left arm of balance. A glass stopper which is having uniform surface was tied to the bottom side of the thread. Below the hanged glass stopper a glass mortar which was clean was placed. In this mortar neatly cleaned 500 ml glass beaker was placed, in which another glass beaker of 50 ml capacity was placed in inverted position and weighed with 50 g to prevent floating. The physical balance was so adjusted that right hand-side was exactly should be 5 g heavier than the left [9].

Ex-Vivo Residence Time Test:

To study the Ex-vivo residence time of tablets the disintegration test apparatus is used. The intestinal mucosa was collected and was cutted into 2x2 size pieces. The cutted pieces were placed on the glass slides and tied with rubber bands. The formulations are placed on the tissue and kept aside for few minutes. Then the glass slides are fitted to the disintegration test apparatus and the apparatus is allowed to start this process is continued for 12 hours. The residence time of each formulation is noted as Ex-vivo residence time [10].

Kinetic Data analysis:

To analyze the release mechanism and release kinetics of the dosage form, the data obtained were fitted into Zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix, Hixon crowell Peppas and aker Lonsdale models.

RESULTS**FT-IR Studies**

Figure 1: IR spectrum of Zidovudine.

Figure 2: IR Spectra of F13.

Table-2: Pre compression parameters of Formulations F1-F13.

Batch code	Bulk density (Mean ± S.D) (g/cc)	Tapped density (Mean ± S.D) (g/cc)	Carr's index (Mean ± S.D) (%)	Hausner's ratio (Mean± S.D)	Angle of repose (Mean±S.D)
F1	0.411 ± 0.001	0.467 ± 0.002	11.87 ± 0.21	1.158 ± 0.005	15.74 ± 0.41
F2	0.420 ± 0.003	0.456 ± 0.004	13.86 ± 0.35	1.142 ± 0.003	14.31 ± 0.43
F3	0.386 ± 0.007	0.435 ± 0.006	15.94 ± 0.23	1.156 ± 0.017	16.52 ± 0.70
F4	0.418 ± 0.007	0.473 ± 0.007	14.51 ± 0.20	1.184 ± 0.025	15.52 ± 0.23
F5	0.406 ± 0.005	0.562 ± 0.009	15.03 ± 1.23	1.196 ± 0.020	16.35 ± 0.18
F6	0.387 ± 0.007	0.404 ± 0.008	12.08 ± 1.32	1.115 ± 0.003	18.43 ± 0.33
F7	0.403 ± 0.008	0.487 ± 0.002	12.46 ± 0.45	1.146 ± 0.005	19.21 ± 0.33
F8	0.382 ± 0.007	0.445 ± 0.006	15.69 ± 0.54	1.156 ± 0.013	17.43 ± 0.21
F9	0.457 ± 0.003	0.491 ± 0.001	14.19 ± 1.30	1.139 ± 0.028	15.74 ± 0.15
F10	0.455 ± 0.008	0.548 ± 0.007	13.35 ± 0.45	1.181 ± 0.011	14.24 ± 0.24
F11	0.380 ± 0.003	0.535 ± 0.002	12.94 ± 0.56	1.136 ± 0.026	17.52 ± 0.45
F12	0.352 ± 0.001	0.403 ± 0.008	13.76 ± 1.67	1.173 ± 0.022	14.52 ± 0.72
F13	0.423 ± 0.002	0.425 ± 0.005	13.47 ± 0.78	1.135 ± 0.023	18.75 ± 0.31

Table-3: Post compression parameters of Formulations F1-F13.

Batch code	Weight variation (%) (Mean ± S.D) (N=20)	Hardness (kg/cm ²) (Mean ± S.D) (N=3)	Thickness (mm) (Mean ± S.D) (N=3)	Friability (%) (Mean ± S.D)	Drug content (%) (Mean ± S.D) (N=3)
F1	301.22 ± 1.508	3.71 ± 0.009	2.98 ± 0.13	0.61	99.35 ± 0.257
F2	300.45 ± 1.082	3.97 ± 0.400	2.91 ± 0.05	0.75	98.37 ± 0.542
F3	298.35 ± 1.006	3.09 ± 0.455	2.76 ± 0.08	0.59	99.42 ± 0.270
F4	300.69 ± 1.222	3.85 ± 0.453	2.81 ± 0.12	0.62	97.81 ± 0.590
F5	303.69 ± 1.428	3.09 ± 0.543	2.74 ± 0.13	0.59	99.98 ± 0.647
F6	301.85 ± 1.348	3.43 ± 0.399	2.29 ± 0.09	0.58	98.12 ± 0.460
F7	300.12 ± 1.876	3.80 ± 0.543	2.85 ± 0.10	0.51	98.87 ± 0.398
F8	299.35 ± 2.002	3.32 ± 0.765	2.71 ± 0.12	0.56	98.56 ± 0.915
F9	301.98 ± 1.982	3.89 ± 0.765	2.87 ± 0.13	0.61	98.95 ± 0.850
F10	299.46 ± 1.118	3.11 ± 0.654	2.68 ± 0.08	0.67	99.21 ± 0.280
F11	300.35 ± 1.676	3.98 ± 0.654	2.69 ± 0.10	0.52	100.65 ± 0.45
F12	299.46 ± 2.111	3.12 ± 0.345	2.91 ± 0.13	0.45	99.59 ± 0.647
F13	303.22 ± 1.234	3.23 ± 0.564	2.43 ± 0.12	0.45	99.19 ± 0.398

Table-4: Swelling Index studies of gastro retentive mucoadhesive tablets of Zidovudine.

TIME(HR)	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
F1	0	18.98	31.21	68.98	111.45	124.45	140.98
F2	0	28.98	42.5	84.5	120.89	154.56	189.89
F3	0	68.98	72.5	104.5	140.89	184.56	259.89
F4	0	10.11	37.14	50.14	71.57	85.14	98.31
F5	0	22.11	37.14	60.14	91.57	119.14	140.31
F6	0	40.11	77.14	90.14	111.57	149.14	180.31
F7	0	12.13	28.76	41.23	65.78	82.34	97.45
F8	0	18.76	30.28	57.67	76.89	93.45	111.23
F9	0	23.45	35.78	68.89	89.87	101.67	134.45
F10	0	24.43	38.88	63.45	96.21	121.56	156.78
F11	0	40.11	77.14	90.14	111.57	149.14	180.31
F12	0	31.23	43.56	87.56	126.78	167.89	198.51
F13	0	78.98	83.45	106.56	154.45	194.56	278.89

Figure 3: Swelling Index studies of gastro retentive mucoadhesive tablets of Zidovudine.

Table-5: *In vitro* mucoadhesion strength & Residence Time of F1-F13.

Batch code	<i>In vitro</i> mucoadhesion strength (g) (Mean \pm SD*)	Ex-Vivo Residence Time Test
F1	18.67	More than 2 hrs
F2	21.89	More than 2 hrs
F3	25.91	More than 2 hrs
F4	20.45	More than 2 hrs
F5	21.79	More than 2 hrs
F6	22.95	More than 2 hrs
F7	20.98	More than 3 hrs
F8	21.45	More than 3 hrs
F9	27.12	More than 4 hrs
F10	21.95	More than 2 hrs
F11	23.09	More than 2 hrs
F12	20.69	More than 2 hrs
F13	26.14	More than 4 hrs

Figure 4: Mucoadhesion strength of Formulations F1-F13.

Table-6: *In vitro* drug release data of formulations F1-F6.

Time (hr)	Cumulative % drug released					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	8.45±1.02	8.34±1.05	6.64±1.11	12.86±0.89	10.78±0.87	8.77±0.98
1	10.91±0.98	9.67±0.76	8.23±1.21	17.34±1.01	14.54±0.98	10.78±1.23
1.5	17.66±0.87	12.58±0.98	10.95±0.97	27±1.79	25.65±1.19	17.89±1.11
2.5	25.49±1.12	20.75±1.11	16.52±1.01	37.51±0.76	34.56±1.22	24.34±1.04
3	35.85±0.98	35.75±1.43	26±1.39	49.78±0.78	42.21±1.01	29.89±0.76
3.5	47.73±1.21	41.8±0.96	33.62±0.87	62.5±1.11	54.45±1.98	43.56±0.98
4	58.59±1.45	51.13±0.84	41.29±0.94	72.31±1.21	60.12±1.67	47.98±0.56
4.5	65.27±1.23	59.52±1.45	52.03±0.67	78.89±1.34	63.45±1.45	56.78±1.21
5	70.64±0.85	62.64±1.56	59.87±1.21	89.87±1.10	76.78±0.78	65.78±1.07
5.5	89.29±0.97	73.74±0.65	63.73±1.23	96.76±0.87	87.78±0.67	73.45±1.19
6	97.24±1.09	80.8±0.99	72.05±1.34	98.78±0.99	96.67±0.56	85.60±1.21
7	100.29±0.98	89.61±1.23	78.37±1.23		99.78±1.34	98.78±1.22
8		94.15±1.09	83.03±1.29			100.98±1.09
9		99.49±0.76	94.77±0.98			
10			99.81±1.79			

Table-7: *In vitro* drug release data of formulations F7-F13.

Time (hr)	Cumulative % drug released						
	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	19.89±1.11	15.67±1.29	10.98±1.09	8.09±0.78	8.89±1.09	8.54±0.67	6.76±0.98
1	32.34±1.29	21.45±1.19	16.89±1.29	12.34±0.85	11.23±1.19	11.11±0.98	10.98±0.85
1.5	43.45±0.98	31.34±1.09	24.78±1.43	17.89±0.98	14.56±1.03	13.34±1.09	12.87±0.78
2.5	55.45±0.56	45.67±0.99	31±0.95	19.89±0.95	20.12±0.98	22.34±1.37	17.89±1.11
3	62.34±1.32	58.89±0.89	42.45±0.89	25.67±1.09	24.56±0.84	27.78±1.11	21.34±1.06
3.5	72.34±1.12	66.78±0.78	52.67±0.67	32.45±1.01	31.23±0.78	32.45±1.01	26.78±0.96
4	83.45±0.87	73.45±1.01	63.56±1.23	45.67±1.21	42.34±1.11	39.89±0.95	30.98±0.87
4.5	96.6±0.78	85.67±1.22	78.89±1.11	55.67±1.03	51.23±1.21	47.98±0.89	37.98±0.86
5	100.87±0.79	90.89±1.32	84.56±1.01	63.45±0.87	60.98±0.59	58.78±0.86	42.34±1.11
5.5		99.89±1.05	92.45±1.05	69.89±0.84	65.5±0.78	60.98±0.96	50.98±1.03
6			99.98±1.34	79.98±0.99	71.23±1.21	65.56±0.99	57.98±0.98
7			100.98±1.09	88.98±1.00	80.98±1.01	78.98±0.98	67.85±0.78
8				91.98±1.21	90.89±1.36	85.56±1.24	73.45±0.67
9				99.99±1.34	96.78±0.87	95.67±1.56	84.56±1.09
10					99.89±0.93	99.98±1.04	93.45±1.06
12							99.98±0.99

Figure 5: dissolution profile for Formulations F1-F6.

Figure 6: dissolution profile for Formulations F7-F13.

Table-8: List of correlation coefficient values (r) for various mathematical models and diffusion coefficient values of Korsmeyer-Peppas's plots for Gastroretentive mucoadhesive tablets of Zidovudine.

Batch Code	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Hixon crowell	Korsmeyer-Peppas	
					n	r
F1	0.992	0.776	0.872	0.876	0.840	0.951
F2	0.993	0.824	0.876	0.899	0.879	0.965
F3	0.992	0.848	0.845	0.867	0.907	0.967
F4	0.980	0.864	0.936	0.967	0.732	0.987
F5	0.990	0.814	0.923	0.896	0.738	0.999
F6	0.997	0.662	0.856	0.844	0.822	0.978
F7	0.967	0.841	0.987	0.934	0.565	0.993
F8	0.981	0.954	0.967	0.908	0.655	0.999
F9	0.989	0.905	0.910	0.868	0.764	0.987
F10	0.990	0.804	0.850	0.845	0.799	0.966
F11	0.992	0.734	0.850	0.876	0.805	0.955
F12	0.993	0.798	0.854	0.822	0.807	0.956
F13	0.981	0.796	0.808	0.833	0.810	0.900

Table-9: Stability studies of the best formulation (F13).

Sampling time (months)	Physical appearance	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Mucoadhesive strength (g)	In vitro drug release at the end of 12hrs (%)
Initial	White	3.23	26.14	99.98
After 1 month	White	3.17	25.14	99.01
After 2 months	White	3.05	25.00	98.99
After 3	White	3.05	24.89	98.15

DISCUSSION

The formulated tablets were subjected for various evaluation parameters like hardness, thickness, weight variation, drug content, determination of swelling index, mucoadhesive strength, Ex-Vivo Residence Time Test and dissolution study. Our experimental results revealed that all the formulated tablets were of good quality with regard to hardness (5- 6 kg/cm²), drug content (> 90%).

The direct relationship was observed between swelling index and polymer concentration. Among the polymers used HPMC K100M showed more swelling compared to Carbopol 934P and NaCMC. HPMC is hydrophilic polymers that swells when contact with water. Formulation containing HPMC K100 M and Carbopol 974P has higher cross linking indicate that polymers having cross linking constrain and therefore the polymer did not open up easily. Formulation containing combination of HPMC and NaCMC showed optimum swelling index Table-6.

The mucoadhesive strength for different formulations was shown in Table-5. Several studies have demonstrated that the bioadhesiveness of tablets depends on the rate of swelling and initial contact time. The highest adhesion force i.e. highest strength of the mucoadhesive bond (27.12) was proposed by F9 containing Carbopol 934P at a concentration of 33%.

The results of *in vitro* drug release studies were shown in Table-6 and 7. The formulations F1, F2, F3 containing HPMC K100M showed complete drug release at 7hrs, 9hrs, 10hrs respectively. The formulations F4, F5, F6 containing NaCMC showed complete drug release at 7hrs, 8hrs, 9hrs respectively. The formulations F7, F8, F9 containing Carbopol 934P showed complete drug release at 6hrs, 7hrs, 8hrs respectively. From the release data it was observed that formulations containing HPMC K100M showed good retardation compared to NaCMC and Carbopol 934P.

Achieve good mucoadhesive strength and retard dissolution combination of polymers were studied. The formulations F10, F11, F12, F13 exhibited good retardation as well as good mucoadhesive strength. Among the four formulations F13 showed complete drug release at 12 hrs containing HPMC K100M and NaCMC showed about 99.98% [13].

Drug release from different formulations was found to depend on polymer viscosity grade and concentration. With an increase in the polymer viscosity and concentration, the release of the drug was found to be retarded. In all the formulations *r* values found higher in zero order models than in first order models indicating release followed zero order kinetics. From the regression values of Higuchi plots it was observed that the drug release was found to be non-Fickian diffusion [14] Table-8. The formulation F13 was found to be stable at 40 °C and 75% RH following a three month stability study Table-9.

CONCLUSION

From this current experimental study of the prepared formulations, it was concluded that gastro retentive mucoadhesive tablets of Zidovudine can be successfully prepared using polymers like HPMC K100M, NaCMC, Carbopol 934P and PVP K30. The polymer concentration and viscosity were found to influence the swelling property and mucoadhesive strength.

It was observed that release of Zidovudine from different formulations was spread over a period of 8-12hrs depending on the polymer's concentration and viscosity. The retardation order of drug release from different polymers is: HPMCK100M>NaCMC>Carbopol 934P. Among all the formulations F13 showed good retardation and found to be stable.

It was concluded that F13 seems to be the promising formulation, providing controlled delivery, for improved bioavailability of Zidovudine.

REFERENCES

1. N.K. Jain, Controlled and novel drug delivery: Mucoadhesive drug delivery; pg.no 370-375.
2. Mathiowitz, E.; Chickering, D. E.; Lehr, C. M. (Eds.). Bioadhesive drug delivery systems: fundamentals, novel approaches, and development. Drugs and the Pharmaceutical Sciences. New York: Marcel Dekker, 1999. 696 p.
3. Sonani NG, Hiremath SP, Dasankoppa FS, Jamakandi VG, Steenivas SA. Design and evaluation of Gastroretentive mucoadhesive Cephalixin tablets. Pharmaceutical development and technology. July 2009; on line.
4. Longer MA, Ching Seng Hung, Robinson JR. Bioadhesive polymers as platforms for oral controlled drug delivery III: Oral Delivery Chlorothiazide using a bioadhesive polymer. J.Pharm. Sci. 1985; 74: 406-411.
5. United States Pharmacopoeia, xxiv NF 19, Rockville: United States Pharmacopoeia Convention. 2000; 2388-9.
6. Raviteja gunda, v v s narayana reddy karri, mahendran baskaran, meghana g. g. n. k. ganesh, a mucoadhesive gastroretentive dosage form for valacyclovir; international journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences issn- 0975-1491 vol 6, issue 9, 2014.
7. Wells J, Aulton ME. Pharmaceutical preformulation. Pharmaceutics: The Science of Dosage Form Design. Eds. 3rd, Edinburgh London: Melbourne and New York. 1988; 224,236,247, 248,250.
8. Leon Lachman, H.A. Lieberman, 3rd Edition , The theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy, Pharmaceutical dosage forms, 296-303
9. Suryakanta Swain, SC Dinda, Sarwar Beg, J. Sruti, Vikas Singh, ME Bhanoji Rao, Design and characterization of oral sustained release mucoadhesive matrix tablets of didanosine; Asian journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research, ajpsr volume 1 issue 2, july 2011.
10. P Perumal and AK Bandyopadhyay, In vitro and in vivo studies on theophylline mucoadhesive drug delivery system; Oriental Pharmacy and Experimental Medicine 2007 7(1), 51-64.
11. Sravani shilpa K et al., Formulation and optimization of Zidovudine Mucoadhesive Tablets Using Synthetic Polymers: IJPFR, Oct-Dec 2011; 1(3): 56-72.
12. M.Sunitha Reddy and Deepthi Dabbeta, Formulation and evaluation of zidovudine sustainedrelease matrix tablets using manilkara zapota gum as a release retarding polymer, *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Volume 4, Issue 10, 1088-1098 ISSN 2277- 7105*.
13. A. S. Gudigenavar¹, L. S. Vijapur¹, C. C. Patil² and R. V. Kulkarni; Development and evaluation of gastro-retentive drug delivery systems of cefuroxime axetil; *African journal of pharmacy and pharmacology; Vol. 7(20), PP. 1332-1338, 29 May 2013*.
14. N. G. Raghavendra Rao, Sunil Firangi, Patel Keyur Formulation and evaluation of gastroretentive effervescent floating drug delivery system of zidovudine; *American Journal of PharmTech Research. 2012; 2(1) ISSN: 2249-338*.

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